

**Report on Consultation on
SECURE Research Career Framework**

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Name
ABIS	Academy of Business in Society
CET	Central European Time
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CRAC-Vitae	Careers Research and Advisory Centre-Vitae
EARTO	European Association of Research and Technology Organisations
EC	European Commission
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, and Occupations
Eurodoc	European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers
HRS4R	Human Resources Strategy for Research
ICoRSA	International Consortium of Research Staff Associations
MCAA	Marie Curie Alumni Association
NCA	Not Currently Affiliated
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
Q	Question
Q&A	Questions and Answers
RCF	Research Career Framework
ReICO	Research and Innovation Careers Observatory
RESAVER	Retirement Savings Vehicle for European Research Institutions
ResearchComp	European Competence Framework for Researchers
RFO	Research-funding Organisation
RPO	Research-performing Organisation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SECURE	Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment
SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
TGB	Technopolis Group Belgium
TTLM	Tenure Track-like Model
EU	European Union
VDI	VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik
YERUN	Young European Research Universities Network

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Executive Summary

This report is deliverable D2.2 of the SECURE project and presents the outcomes of the public consultation on the first draft of the SECURE Research Career Framework (RCF). The report is closely linked to deliverable D3.2 of the SECURE project which similarly presents the outcomes of the public consultation on the first draft of the SECURE Tenure Track-like Models (TTLMs). The feedback gathered from the consultation helped to revise and finalise the SECURE RCF and TTLMs.

1. Introduction

This report is deliverable D2.2 of the SECURE project [1] and presents the **outcomes of the public consultation on the first draft of the SECURE Research Career Framework (RCF)** [2]. The report is linked to deliverable D3.2 of the SECURE project [3] which similarly presents the outcomes of the public consultation on the first draft of the SECURE Tenure Track-like Models (TTLMs) [4]. The aim of the consultation is to gather feedback from the research community on these 2 drafts in order to revise and finalise the RCF [5] and TTLMs [6]. The final versions of the RCF and TTLMs will hereby also take into account the lessons learned from the SECURE trials to implement the RCF [7].

The **first draft of the SECURE RCF** took an initial step towards implementing Council Recommendation C/2023/1640 of 18 December 2023 on a European Framework to Attract and Retain Research, Innovation, and Entrepreneurial Talents in Europe [8]. The first draft of the RCF is structured around the 8 pillars and 44 recommendations of the Council Recommendation and is aimed at research-performing organisations (RPOs) and research-funding organisations (RFOs). The first draft of the RCF proposed an initial comprehensive set of 103 actions for RPOs and RFOs to implement the Council Recommendation and improve research careers at their organisations.

The **public consultation** consisted of a series of consultation meetings with research stakeholders and a consultation survey on the first draft of the SECURE RCF. The 3 online meetings were targeted at researchers, representatives of research organisations, and representatives of industry. The online survey was open to all research stakeholders but was targeted especially at researchers. The actions of the RCF were presented in the meetings and survey whereby participants were asked to identify priorities and gaps as well as offer suggestions to improve the actions in the RCF. The consultation served not only to collect feedback but also to already raise awareness of the RCF.

This report first describes the main aims, structure, and outcomes of each of the **consultation meetings** for researchers, research organisations, and industry (Section 2). The report then presents the main aims, structure, and outcomes of the **consultation survey** (Section 3). The report closes with a brief **conclusion** of the next steps to revise and finalise the RCF (Section 4).

2. Consultation Meetings

2.1. Consultation Methodology

There were **3 consultation meetings** whereby each meeting was aimed at a specific stakeholder:

- Consultation for Researchers on 16 September 2024
- Consultation for Research Organisations on 17 September 2024
- Consultation for Industry Representatives on 25 September 2024.

A **registration form** was created for each consultation meeting on the Zoom platform (whereby the registration links are now defunct) and was shared via the SECURE project social media and via the networks of the SECURE consortium partners. Specific partners also directly engaged their members to encourage participation in the meetings whereby Eurodoc, ICoRSA, and MCAA invited researchers to the researcher meeting, YERUN invited universities to the research organisation meeting, and ABIS invited companies to the industry meeting. Separate **privacy policies** also needed to be developed for each consultation meeting which conformed with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) due to some participant personal data being collected [9] [10] [11].

A general **agenda** was developed for the meetings which was planned for a duration of 2 hours from 10.00 to 12.00 each day and which first introduced the SECURE RCF and then consisted of 2 break-out sessions on specific discussion topics and a final plenary debrief as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Agenda for SECURE Consultation Meetings

10:00 - 10:00	Welcome and Opening
10:05 - 10:20	Introduction to SECURE Research Career Framework
10:20 - 10:25	Transition to Break-out Sessions
10:25 - 10:55	Break-out Session 1
10:55 - 11:00	Short Break
11:00 - 11:30	Break-out Session 2
11:30 - 11:50	Plenary Debrief
11:50 - 12:00	Q&A and Closing

2.2. Consultation for Researchers

The **consultation for researchers** was held online on the Zoom platform on 16 September 2024 from 10:00 to 12:00 CEST and was organised and hosted by YERUN with Gareth O'Neill (TGB) as lead facilitator who was supported by break-out room facilitators Katarina Haluskova (ABIS), Silvia Gomez Recio (YERUN), Sanja Terlević (YERUN), and Emma Day (CRAC-Vitae). A total of 42 out of 45 registered participants consisting of early-career and senior researchers attended the webinar. The main aim of the meeting was to engage researchers in open discussion on the first draft of the RCF and to gather their feedback on the main challenges which they are facing in their research careers as well as how to improve research careers and specifically how to improve the actions of the RCF.

The first meeting for researchers focused on first setting the background and then maximising the discussion with researchers (see Annex 1 for the meeting slides). The **SECURE project** was introduced followed by an explanation of the **Council Recommendation**, relevant **European support measures** for research careers, and the **first draft of the SECURE RCF**. The participants were then divided into **5 break-out groups** focused on specific topics which were selected by the participants in advance of the meeting (who could change rooms if they wished). Break-out session #1 focused on **Alternative Careers**, session #2 on **Skills Development**, session #3 on **Working Conditions**, session #4 on **Research Assessment**, and session #5 on **Tenure Track-like Models**.

The **break-out groups** were moderated by a facilitator from the SECURE project who first gave a brief introduction to the specific topic of the break-out session which was structured around key actions proposed in the SECURE RCF related to that topic and which was focused on the relevance for researchers. The moderator then led the discussion and encouraged the researchers to give their views on the topic and suggestions to improve the actions of the RCF related to that topic. The researchers were also asked to provide any additional feedback they might have for the RCF. The moderators took detailed notes of all main points and recommendations to improve the RCF. The key outcomes of the meeting are summarised below for each of the break-out session topics.

Alternative Careers

- The term 'alternative careers' is problematic as it suggests that these paths are secondary to academic careers yet the majority of doctoral graduates will ultimately leave academia
- Organisations need to offer better career development support for non-linear and hybrid career paths and help researchers prepare for careers both inside and outside academia

- Organisations need to foster entrepreneurial skills and facilitate intersectoral mobility
- Intersectoral mobility is a positive development but needs to be balanced with job stability.

Skills Development

- Organisations need to ensure that researchers formally have enough time to develop skills/competences whereby there are existing good practices available to learn from
- Researchers are mostly unfamiliar with ResearchComp [12] but when ResearchComp is explained then they regard it as a useful tool to identify and develop skills/competencies
- Organisations need to integrate ResearchComp into their policies and programmes for skills development of researchers despite resistance to change or lack of (human) resources
- Skills development needs to be recognised and rewarded in the career progression of researchers (especially transferable skills such as collaboration and self-management).

Working Conditions

- Improving working conditions of researchers and increasing the number of permanent or open-ended contracts and providing better (access to) better social benefits is a top priority
- The work-life balance of researchers needs to be safeguarded across a range of relevant topics including (invisible) working hours, mental health issues, and (supervisor) harassment
- Researchers need to be more involved and supported to engage in relevant governance and policy-making bodies as well as to engage with senior leadership at their organisations
- Setting a maximum number for (successive) temporary contracts for researchers at organisations should not limit their career progression or employment opportunities
- Doctoral candidates should be seen and treated not as students but rather as professionals with a commensurate employment status, remuneration, and (access to) social benefits.

Research Assessment

- A balanced approach to research assessment is needed which consists of both a qualitative and (responsible) quantitative approach when researchers are being evaluated
- Research assessment needs to include the diversity of researcher activities (and not only focus on publications) including proposal writing, project management, and leadership
- Research funders need to play a more central role in shaping research assessment practices and recognise the diversity of research activities beyond publications in their evaluations

- Organisations need to ensure uniform assessment when evaluating researchers and inform researcher evaluators of any reformed assessment criteria and then assess the assessment
- More attention needs to be given in research assessment to societal outreach and impact.

Tenure Track-like Models

- Researchers have mixed responses on tenure track-like models and note that they are not the only solution to precarity and suggest longer contracts as a more practical alternative
- Tenure track-like models need to be flexible and adaptable to different career paths (including for both research and education) and should not restrict researcher mobility
- There needs to be more transparency and information provided openly and in advance on relevant career progression procedures and tenure track-like models at organisations
- Organisations need to be more transparent and raise awareness among their researchers on their (overall) actual number of available tenure track-like positions and professorships.

2.3. Consultation for Research Organisations

The **consultation for research organisations** was held online on the Zoom platform on 17 September 2024 from 10:00 to 12:00 CEST and was organised and hosted by YERUN with Gareth O'Neill (TGB) as lead facilitator who was supported by break-out room facilitators Katarina Haluskova (ABIS), Silvia Gomez Recio (YERUN), Sanja Terlević (YERUN), and Emma Day (CRAC-Vitae). A total of 40 out of 51 registered participants consisting of representatives of RPOs, RFOs, and research and technology organisations (RTOs) attended the webinar. The main aim of the meeting was to engage research organisations in open discussion on the first draft of the RCF and to gather their feedback on the main challenges facing research organisations in improving research careers and reducing precarity and specifically how to improve the actions of the RCF.

The second meeting for research organisations focused on first setting the background and then maximising the discussion with the research organisations (see Annex 2 for the meeting slides). The **SECURE project** was introduced followed by an explanation of the **Council Recommendation**, relevant **European support measures** for research careers, and the **first draft of the SECURE RCF**. The participants were then divided into **5 break-out groups** on specific topics which were chosen by the participants beforehand (who could change rooms if they wished). Break-out session #1 focused on **Alternative Careers**, session #2 on **Skills Development**, session #3 on **Working Conditions**, session #4 on **Research Assessment**, and session #5 on **Tenure Track-like Models**.

The **break-out groups** were moderated by a facilitator from the SECURE project who first gave a brief introduction to the specific topic of the break-out session which was structured around key actions proposed in the SECURE RCF related to that topic and which was focused on the relevance for research organisations. The moderator then led the discussion and encouraged the participants to give their views on the topic and suggestions to improve the actions of the RCF related to that topic. The participants were also asked for any additional feedback they might have for the RCF. The moderators took detailed notes of all main points and recommendations to improve the RCF. The key outcomes of the meeting are summarised below for each of the break-out session topics.

Alternative Careers

- The term 'alternative careers' needs to be reframed as 'careers beyond academia' to reflect the fact that such careers are not necessarily alternative but simply non-academic careers
- A culture change is needed which values a broader range of career paths beyond academia
- Careers outside of academia are equally impactful as careers in academia and need to be promoted as integral career paths within the research and innovation careers ecosystem
- Organisations need to prioritise training for intersectoral collaboration and mobility, fostering entrepreneurial skills, and encouraging academia-industry partnerships
- Researchers need to be supported in translating their research into practical applications
- Early-career researchers need to be informed early about their realistic career chances in academia so that their expectations are managed and they can prepare for future careers.

Skills Development

- ResearchComp is a useful tool which can complement existing training programmes but there may be challenges in translating the (many) skills/competences into actual practices
- Organisations need to raise awareness about ResearchComp among their researchers and especially focus on transferable skills to help researchers in their professional development
- Organisations need to ensure guaranteed time and support for the skills development of their researchers as research activities are typically prioritised over skills development
- Organisations need to tailor their skills development to the different research disciplines.

Working Conditions

- The precarity of research careers is a top priority which organisations need to address
- Inconsistent funding models and short-term contracts are key barriers to career stability

- There needs to be a change in research culture with a focus on improving the rights of researchers, more diversity and inclusivity, professional development, and work-life balance
- Human resources offices need to be strengthened to improve their support for researchers
- The rights and conditions of researchers need to be comparable with other top professions
- Organisations need to improve support for research managers and research technicians.

Research Assessment

- Both qualitative and quantitative approaches are needed for the assessment of researchers
- Research assessment needs to focus on the quality of research not the amount of outputs
- Peer review is a critical and necessary instrument for assessing the quality of researcher
- There are legal and structural barriers which can hinder the reform of research assessment
- High-level policy commitments are needed at national level to reform research assessment
- Research assessment needs to go beyond academia and include wider impacts on society
- Research funders could be pivotal agents of change in the reform of research assessment
- Researchers need to be directly involved in shaping the reforms of research assessment

Tenure Track-like Models

- Tenure track-like models are a solution to addressing the precarity of research careers
- Tenure track-like models need to support the professional development of researchers
- Researchers on tenure track-like models could benefit from mentors at their organisations
- The goals and procedures for implementing new tenure track-like models should be clear
- Best practices on existing tenure track-like models could support reforms at organisations.

2.4. Consultation for Industry Representatives

The **consultation for industry representatives** was held online on the Zoom platform on 25 September 2024 from 10:00 to 12:00 CEST and was organised and hosted by ABIS with Gareth O'Neill (TGB) as lead facilitator who was supported by discussion topic facilitators Katarina Haluskova (ABIS), Sanja Terlević (YERUN), and Emma Day (CRAC-Vitae). A total of 6 out of 25 registered participants from industry attended the webinar. The main aim of the meeting was to engage companies in open discussion on the first draft of the RCF and on the challenges facing companies in improving research careers and specifically how to improve the actions of the RCF.

An overall **low turnout of industry representatives** for the webinar was expected due to the experience of project partners in engaging companies on research careers and the focus of the project on improving research careers and trialing actions at academic organisations but the actual low turnout was still surprising given the much higher number of registered participants. Extra effort had even been made to contact companies to join the webinar including via a network of 800 business contacts from ABIS and 60 additional research-intensive business contacts from desk research and LinkedIn by ABIS. All registered participants were contacted after the webinar by ABIS to understand the low turnout and respondents explained that they had either registered out of interest but needed to prioritise other commitments on the day or that they were uncertain of the relevance of their contributions on how to make research careers more attractive and sustainable.

The final meeting for industry representatives focused on setting the background and maximising the discussion with the participants (see Annex 3 for the meeting slides). The **SECURE project** was first introduced followed by an explanation of the **Council Recommendation**, relevant **European support measures** for research careers, and the **first draft of the SECURE RCF**. The original intention was to include 3 break-out groups focused on topics relevant for industry but due to the low turnout all **3 topics** were discussed in **one plenary session** with participants. Topic #1 focused on **Alternative Careers**, topic #2 on **Skills Development**, and topic #3 on **Working Conditions**.

Alternative Careers

- Mobility across disciplines, sectors, and countries can be an enriching experience and bring substantial benefits to researchers but should not be made compulsory for researchers (especially for senior researchers who prioritise stability in their careers over mobility)
- It is extremely difficult for a researcher to return to academia once they have left academia
- Research assessment in academia is focused on peer-reviewed publications which is not a priority outside of academia and this can hinder intersectoral collaboration and mobility
- Industry professionals are often not able to co-author peer-reviewed publications when they collaborate with academic researchers due to internal regulations at their companies.

Skills Development

- Researchers need to understand and be able to clearly communicate their acquired skills/competences and expertise when applying for employment in the non-academic sector

- Researchers need to be able to recognise their strengths and could boost their confidence and ability to gain employment in the non-academic sector by clearly branding themselves
- ResearchComp could help researchers to understand and translate their acquired skills/competences into industry language when communication with potential employers
- Researchers are generally not aware of the existence and the value of ResearchComp.

Working Conditions

- Researchers are mainly looking for stability and meaningful recognition in their careers
- Researchers typically transition to the non-academic sector due to more competitive remuneration, more flexibility, better work-life balance, and more respectful treatment
- Researchers feel that academic researchers are undervalued by their organisations and that early-career researchers are especially treated as a disposable workplace in academia.

2.5. Additional Input from Industry Representatives

Due to the low turnout of the consultation for industry representatives ABIS reached out to several of their business members for **additional input from industry** and held a one-on-one call with **BrainZell** on 17 December 2024 [13]. Brainzell is a life sciences start-up with 7 employees of whom 6 have PhDs. The company was founded by former academic researchers from Karolinska Institute who transitioned to industry due to a lack of clear career pathways in academia. Brainzell provided feedback on the 3 topics of **Alternative Careers**, **Skills Development**, and **Working Conditions**.

Alternative Careers

- Industry offers a viable and attractive alternative career path for researchers who may need to leave academia or may not find long-term stability or growth opportunities in academia
- Research careers in industry often help researchers to see real-world impact of their work
- Collaborative programmes with industry such as internships and secondments could help doctoral candidates and postdoctoral researchers (prepare for a) transition to industry
- Collaborative programmes with industry need to provide funding to stimulate and support start-ups and SMEs to hire researchers on short-term intersectoral mobility exchanges
- Industry recognises different titles for research-related professions than used in academia
- Researchers are unlikely to return to academia once they have transitioned to industry due to better remuneration, better job stability, and more career opportunities in industry

- Companies prefer to hire doctoral graduates for research roles due to their skills/competences and the complexity and specialisation required in emerging technologies.

Skills Development

- Researchers from academia often lack awareness of and training in industry-specific skills
- Researchers from academia often lack the project management skills required in industry
- Companies typically value good project management skills more than entrepreneurship
- The ability to work within time constraints is vital in industry which works on tight timelines
- Companies usually support the continuous professional development of their researchers
- Companies often encourage and support their researchers to attend scientific conferences and events to stay up to date on cutting-edge research and to present their own research.

Working Conditions

- Industry typically offers more competitive remuneration and better working conditions than academia which can be a key factor in attracting and retaining academic researchers
- Companies may offer stock options as part of a long-term incentive to attract and retain researchers which can foster a sense of ownership and alignment with company success
- Companies may offer regular feedback sessions with their researchers on job performance
- Typical performance indicators in industry are related to patents and products developed
- Companies often align annual job evaluations of researchers with reviews of remuneration.

Additional **input from an industry perspective** was provided by the European Association of Research and Technology Organisations (**EARTO**) [14] in written form to the SECURE project via the European Commission. EARTO represents the interests of more than 350 research and technology organisations (RTOs) and more than 150,000 highly skilled researchers and engineers in over 20 European countries. EARTO is committed to improving the intersectoral and international mobility and careers of researchers and engineers. EARTO provided feedback on the 3 topics of **Definition of Researchers and Research Careers, Funding and Flexibility**, and **Researcher Mobility**.

Definition of Researchers and Research Careers

- The R1-R4 researcher profiles [15] do not align with the actual career structures of RTOs or industry which require more flexible profiles and mappings for their careers structures

- Research careers in RTOs and industry often involve non-linear career paths and blend research, innovation, and entrepreneurial activities which need to be duly recognised
- Professional career planning needs substantial investment in human and financial resources
- The recognition of research impact should extend beyond academic outputs to include applied research and innovation outputs which are more relevant for RTOs and industry.

Funding and Flexibility

- European and national funding systems need to integrate career development into project funding as fellowships are not suitable for all organisations due to national legal restrictions
- Funding mechanisms need to be flexible enough to align with the different operating models of RTOs and companies as well as to align with country-specific requirements

Researcher Mobility

- European and national regulations can pose significant challenges to researcher mobility
- Tax, social security, and employment laws make cross-border work complex and impractical
- Dual positions across countries can incur high costs, administrative burdens, and tax issues
- Residence permits for mobile researchers need to be mutually recognised across Europe.

3. Consultation Survey

3.1. Survey Methodology

The **Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework 2024** was published openly in the EU Survey Tool [16] and ran from 09 December 2024 until 19 January 2025. The consultation survey was aimed primarily at all stages of researchers as well as at research-related employees and representatives of RPOs and RFOs. The survey was created to gather feedback from the research community specifically on the first draft of the SECURE RCF and TTLMs and more generally on how to improve research careers and reduce the precarity of researchers. The survey consisted of single choice and open response questions and was planned to take around 20-30 minutes to complete. The feedback from survey respondents will contribute to revising and finalising the RCF and TTLMs.

The consultation survey is **structured around the first draft of the RCF** which in turn is aligned with the 8 pillars of the European Framework for Research Careers in the Council Recommendation as shown in Figure 1. The survey is divided into 12 sections whereby §1 gives a brief introduction to the survey and survey privacy policy [17], §2 asks for biographical data on respondents, §3-10 asks respondents to prioritise and give their views on the 103 actions across the 8 pillars, §11 asks questions focusing on TTLMs, and §12 thanks respondents for their feedback (see Annex 4 for the full survey). Survey respondents could select 3 types of priorities for the actions: TOP priority for critical actions; HIGH priority for important actions; and LOW priority for less relevant actions.

Figure 1 - European Framework for Research Careers

Pillar 1 Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area #1-6	Pillar 2 Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers #7-10	Pillar 3 Recruitment and Working Conditions #11-15	Pillar 4 Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation #16-25
Pillar 5 Career Assessment, Development, and Progression #26-30	Pillar 6 Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination #31-32	Pillar 7 Support Actions for Research Careers #33-39	Pillar 8 Monitoring of Research Careers #40-44

The **prioritisations of the actions** will serve to identify which of the actions of the first draft of the RCF (which are aimed at RPOs and RFOs) are important from the perspective of researchers. In the next stage of the project the structure of the RCF (which is now structured around the pillars of the European Framework for Research Careers) and the actions of the RCF (which formed an initial list of actions to test and trial for their usefulness) will be revised based on the feedback from the consultation and lessons learned from the trial organisations. The prioritisations will serve as a guide when the SECURE consortium is revising the structure and actions of the RCF whereby actions will be framed in an order of importance based on their TOP, HIGH, or LOW priority status.

3.2. Survey Outcomes

A total of **323 respondents** filled in the survey who consisted further of **239 researchers** (74%), 44 research managers (14%), 0 research technicians (0%), 12 research support staff (4%), 7 policymakers (2%), and 21 individuals with other professions (6%). This report further focuses on summaries of the responses from the researchers as this group was the primary target of the survey and is considered the most important for feedback to revise the RCF and TTLMs. Relevant responses and comments from the other respondents will also be taken into account where the responses are relevant when revising and finalising the final version of the RCF and TTLMs.

Regarding the **gender** of the 239 researchers: 101 identified as male (42%), 132 identified as female (55%), 4 identified as other (2%), and 2 individuals wished not to disclose their gender (1%). There was thus a reasonable gender balance across the survey respondents. Regarding the **career stage** of the 239 researchers: 55 were R1 or early-career researchers who conduct research under supervision (23%), 44 were R2 or early-career researchers who have experience but are not yet independent (18%), 95 were R3 or senior researchers who develop their own research (40%), and 45 were R4 or senior researchers who are recognised as leading their research field (19%). More senior researchers interestingly responded to the survey than early-career researchers.

Regarding the main **research discipline** of the 239 researchers: 12 were from agricultural sciences (5%), 51 were from engineering and technology (21%), 20 were from humanities (8%), 37 were from medical and health sciences (16%), 43 were from natural sciences (18%), 51 were from social sciences (21%), and 25 did not disclose their research (as they had originally identified as individuals with another profession who did not need to disclose their research discipline but were then reclassified as researchers from their description of their job titles) (11%). All main research disciplines were thus represented in the responses albeit in varying degrees of representation.

Regarding the **type of organisation** for which the 239 researchers work: 184 worked at a university (77%), 40 worked at a research institute (16%), 1 worked at a research association (>1%), 2 worked for the government (1%), 2 worked at a non-profit organisation (1%), 6 worked at a company (3%), and 4 individuals worked at other organisations (2%). The majority of respondents thus work at a university or research institute. Regarding the **country of residence** of the 239 researchers: 51 lived in Romania (21%), 37 lived in Italy (16%), 23 lived in Portugal (10%), 22 lived in Croatia (9%), 10 lived Ireland (4%), 9 lived in Sweden (4%), 17 were from several other countries in the European Union (7%), and 70 were from several countries outside of the European Union (29%).

The survey responses on the **priorities for the 103 actions** of the first draft of the RCF for the 239 researchers are detailed below for each of the survey questions across the 8 pillars whereby the numbers for the TOP, HIGH, and LOW priorities and overall priority for each action are identified. **TOP** priority refers hereby to actions which are critical for improving research careers, **HIGH** priority refers to actions which are important (but are not critical) for improving research careers, and **LOW** priority refers to actions which are seen as less important for improving research careers. It should be noted that many free responses were also received in the survey on the topics of the RCF and TTLMs which are not presented here but which will be taken into account where relevant.

Pillar 1 - Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area

How would you prioritise the following actions on the definition of a 'researcher'? (Q10)

Adopt the EFfRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies	TOP 77	HIGH 123	LOW 39
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Communicate more clearly on definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'	TOP 115	HIGH 104	LOW 20
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How would you prioritise the following actions on intersectoral mobility? (Q11)

Raise awareness on the wide diversity of research careers in and outside academia	TOP 92	HIGH 128	LOW 19
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Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	TOP 135	HIGH 89	LOW 15
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Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector	TOP 109	HIGH 104	LOW 26
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Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers	TOP 80	HIGH 112	LOW 47
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Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility	TOP 108	HIGH 98	LOW 33
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Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	TOP 90	HIGH 119	LOW 30
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How would you prioritise the following actions on research managers? (Q12)

Define a clear profile for research manager positions with their roles and responsibilities	TOP 109	HIGH 100	LOW 30
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Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research manager as a research career	TOP 79	HIGH 123	LOW 37
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Train researchers in research management and support transition to research manager	TOP 101	HIGH 111	LOW 27
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Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research managers	TOP 112	HIGH 103	LOW 24
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How would you prioritise the following actions on research technicians? (Q13)

Define a clear profile for research technician positions with their roles and responsibilities	TOP 85	HIGH 119	LOW 35
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Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research technician as a research career	TOP 71	HIGH 127	LOW 41
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Train researchers in technical support and support transition to research technician	TOP 94	HIGH 116	LOW 29
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Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research technicians	TOP 101	HIGH 114	LOW 24
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How would you prioritise the following actions on the R1-R4 profiles? (Q14)

Adopt the R1-R4 profiles or map existing organisational profiles onto the R1-R4 profiles	TOP 68	HIGH 119	LOW 52
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Refer to the R1-R4 profiles in job/grant advertisements and relevant communications	TOP 71	HIGH 118	LOW 50
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Identify scope of precarity and propose measures to reduce precarity for R1-R4 profiles	TOP 102	HIGH 108	LOW 29
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Treat doctoral candidates as professionals with related working conditions and benefits	TOP 131	HIGH 85	LOW 23
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Raise awareness of and support adoption of R1-R4 profiles in the non-academic sector	TOP 72	HIGH 110	LOW 57
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How would you prioritise the following actions on the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles? (Q15)

Adopt the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles in organisational regulations and policies	TOP 65	HIGH 124	LOW 50
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Tailor support measures for career development to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups	TOP 90	HIGH 114	LOW 35
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Tailor support measures to address precarity to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups	TOP 90	HIGH 119	LOW 30
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Pillar 2 - Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers

How would you prioritise the following actions on career recognition/interoperability? (Q17)

Track the long-term career paths of researchers at and beyond home organisations	TOP 71	HIGH 130	LOW 38
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Collect and share best practices on recognition and support of diverse research careers	TOP 86	HIGH 123	LOW 30
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Engage with key stakeholders on recognition and support of diverse research careers	TOP 91	HIGH 115	LOW 33
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Engage with key stakeholders on interoperability and comparability of research careers	TOP 76	HIGH 127	LOW 36
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How would you prioritise the following actions on career pathways? (Q18)

Raise awareness on non-linear and hybrid research career paths among researchers	TOP 90	HIGH 116	LOW 33
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Integrate non-linear and hybrid research career paths into regulations and policies	TOP 88	HIGH 112	LOW 39
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Offer career development support for non-linear and hybrid research career paths	TOP 95	HIGH 118	LOW 26
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Collect and share best practices on non-linear and hybrid research career paths	TOP 68	HIGH 127	LOW 44
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How would you prioritise the following actions on the ESCO classification? (Q19)

Integrate (updates of) the ESCO classification into research job/grant advertisements	TOP 60	HIGH 123	LOW 56
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Integrate (updates of) ESCO classification into local/national accreditation frameworks	TOP 57	HIGH 118	LOW 64
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Identify changing and emerging skills/competences, qualifications, and occupations	TOP 81	HIGH 110	LOW 48
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Provide recommendations for future revisions of classifications in the ESCO classification	TOP 63	HIGH 112	LOW 64
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How would you prioritise the following actions on human resources? (Q20)

Conduct a review of research career structures and career paths within organisation	TOP 90	HIGH 105	LOW 44
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Involve human resources officers and research staff in organisational R1-R4 mapping	TOP 71	HIGH 116	LOW 52
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Develop clear documentation, guidelines, and communications on the R1-R4 mapping	TOP 101	HIGH 92	LOW 46
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Engage with other human resources offices to share best practices on the R1-R4 profiles	TOP 57	HIGH 118	LOW 64
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Pillar 3 - Recruitment and Working Conditions

How would you prioritise the following actions on recruitment/selection? (Q22)

Make general recruitment and selection procedures for vacant positions publicly available	TOP 131	HIGH 88	LOW 20
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Provide individual feedback to candidates on result of a specific recruitment and selection	TOP 130	HIGH 92	LOW 17
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Inform recruiters and selectors on the value of alternative career paths and career breaks	TOP 101	HIGH 112	LOW 26
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How would you prioritise the following actions on working conditions? (Q23)

Review and internally discuss providing commensurate remuneration for researchers	TOP 124	HIGH 97	LOW 18
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Review and improve support for flexible working conditions and work-life balance	TOP 146	HIGH 77	LOW 16
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Review and improve support for inclusivity, equal opportunities, and gender equality	TOP 104	HIGH 104	LOW 31
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Review and improve support for academic freedom and protection against interference	TOP 122	HIGH 95	LOW 22
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Review and improve support to researchers with the fulfilment of administrative duties	TOP 105	HIGH 107	LOW 27
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Review and internally discuss providing more permanent contracts to researchers	TOP 156	HIGH 72	LOW 11
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Define a maximum threshold for number of fixed-term contracts and monitoring plan	TOP 82	HIGH 109	LOW 48
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Review and internally discuss researcher access to relevant social protection benefits	TOP 127	HIGH 90	LOW 22
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Collect and share best practices on improving the working conditions for researchers	TOP 110	HIGH 103	LOW 26
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How would you prioritise the following actions on rights/obligations? (Q24)

Raise awareness regularly on social protection rights and obligations to all researchers	TOP 119	HIGH 96	LOW 24
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Provide individual personalised counselling on social protection rights and obligations	TOP 88	HIGH 111	LOW 40
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Collaborate with external specialists in field of social protection rights and obligations	TOP 75	HIGH 106	LOW 58
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How would you prioritise the following actions on pensions/RESAVER? (Q25)

Raise awareness about long-term pension planning and RESAVER among researchers	TOP 109	HIGH 99	LOW 31
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Take part in RESAVER Pension Fund and join the consortium of member organisations	TOP 84	HIGH 106	LOW 49
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Pillar 4 - Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation

How would you prioritise the following actions on doctoral training? (Q27)

Align doctoral training programmes with Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training	TOP 103	HIGH 99	LOW 37
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Align doctoral training programmes with European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	TOP 122	HIGH 82	LOW 35
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Integrate policies and practices for Open Science into doctoral training programmes	TOP 106	HIGH 96	LOW 37
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How would you prioritise the following actions on ResearchComp? (Q28)

Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences for researchers	TOP 88	HIGH 116	LOW 35
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Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers	TOP 81	HIGH 113	LOW 45
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Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies	TOP 70	HIGH 110	LOW 59
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Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences	TOP 73	HIGH 104	LOW 62
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Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp	TOP 68	HIGH 109	LOW 62
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How would you prioritise the following actions on entrepreneurship? (Q29)

Raise awareness on entrepreneurship taking an inclusive and gender equal approach	TOP 75	HIGH 100	LOW 64
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Encourage, train, and support researchers for entrepreneurship, start-ups, and spin-offs	TOP 97	HIGH 94	LOW 48
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Create support offices, hubs, and centres for entrepreneurship and technology transfer	TOP 93	HIGH 96	LOW 50
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How would you prioritise the following actions on interdisciplinary mobility? (Q30)

Encourage, train, and support researchers for interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility	TOP 139	HIGH 87	LOW 13
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Collect and share best practices on supporting interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility	TOP 95	HIGH 120	LOW 24
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Pillar 5 - Career Assessment, Development, and Progression

How would you prioritise the following actions on mobility recognition? (Q32)

Recognise international collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	TOP 131	HIGH 88	LOW 20
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Recognise intersectoral collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	TOP 109	HIGH 111	LOW 19
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Recognise interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	TOP 121	HIGH 102	LOW 16
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Recognise virtual collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	TOP 85	HIGH 109	LOW 45
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How would you prioritise the following actions on research assessment? (Q33)

Integrate a qualitative and responsible quantitative approach into research assessment	TOP 100	HIGH 118	LOW 21
Recognise diversity of roles, activities, and outputs of researchers in research assessment	TOP 118	HIGH 104	LOW 17
Recognise research manager and research management activities in research assessment	TOP 90	HIGH 116	LOW 33
Recognise research technician and technical support activities in research assessment	TOP 80	HIGH 119	LOW 40
Recognise research integrity and inclusivity and gender equality in research assessment	TOP 92	HIGH 110	LOW 37
Recognise Open Science practices and societal impact of research in research assessment	TOP 101	HIGH 106	LOW 32
Inform research assessors on the added value of reformed research assessment criteria	TOP 79	HIGH 117	LOW 43
Monitor any reforms in research assessment criteria for negative and unwanted effects	TOP 89	HIGH 116	LOW 34

How would you prioritise the following actions on assessment initiatives? (Q34)

Sign the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and join CoARA as a member	TOP 59	HIGH 116	LOW 64
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Identify structural and administrative barriers to reform research assessment systems	TOP 88	HIGH 116	LOW 35
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Collect and share best practices on reforming existing research assessment systems	TOP 69	HIGH 126	LOW 44
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How would you prioritise the following actions on career support? (Q35)

Review and improve the career support and professional development of researchers	TOP 137	HIGH 90	LOW 12
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Provide professional mentoring to researchers by experts in and outside the organisation	TOP 117	HIGH 94	LOW 28
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How would you prioritise the following actions on TTLMs? (Q36)

Review regulations and status of TTLMs in national context and locally at organisations	TOP 74	HIGH 127	LOW 38
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Define TTLMs in discussion and close collaboration with researchers at organisations	TOP 82	HIGH 118	LOW 21
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Develop an action plan for future implementation of defined TTLMs at organisations	TOP 74	HIGH 126	LOW 39
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Engage with key stakeholders on TTLMs to collect and share best practices on TTLMs	TOP 61	HIGH 130	LOW 48
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Engage with national research-funding bodies on need for long-term funding for TTLMs	TOP 88	HIGH 113	LOW 38
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Pillar 6 - Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination

How would you prioritise the following actions on a competitive European Union? (Q38)

Review and internally discuss support to attract and reintegrate returning researchers	TOP 112	HIGH 99	LOW 28
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Review and internally discuss support to facilitate dual positions in different countries	TOP 98	HIGH 104	LOW 37
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Engage with key stakeholders to contribute to the balanced circulation of researchers	TOP 94	HIGH 100	LOW 45
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Pillar 7 - Support Actions for Research Careers

How would you prioritise the following actions on talent platforms? (Q40)

Raise awareness on the EURAXESS portal and ERA Talent Platform among researchers	TOP 90	HIGH 119	LOW 30
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Disseminate job/grant opportunities in the EURAXESS portal and ERA Talent Platform	TOP 119	HIGH 92	LOW 28
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How would you prioritise the following actions on the European Charter for Researchers? (Q41)

Raise awareness on the revised Charter among researchers	TOP 101	HIGH 114	LOW 24
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Endorse and implement the revised Charter at organisations	TOP 108	HIGH 103	LOW 28
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How would you prioritise the following actions on the HRS4R award? (Q42)

Raise awareness on the HRS4R award and its relevance for researchers	TOP 85	HIGH 113	LOW 41
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Apply formally to receive the HRS4R award to the European Commission	TOP 79	HIGH 110	LOW 50
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Pillar 8 - Monitoring of Research Careers.

How would you prioritise the following actions on ReICO? (Q44)

Engage with OECD and key stakeholders on development and implementation of ReICO	TOP 68	HIGH 119	LOW 52
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Review and internally discuss collection and provision of relevant internal data for ReICO	TOP 62	HIGH 124	LOW 53
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4. Conclusion

The **consultation on the first draft of the SECURE RCF and TTLMs was successful** in the high number of participants and engaged discussions in the consultation meetings and the high number of respondents and targeted responses from researchers in the consultation survey. The public consultation was intended to gather feedback on the first version of the RCF and TTLMs in order to test the viability and usefulness of the RCF and TTLMs and ensure that the RCF and TTLMs address the interests and needs of researchers to improve research careers and reduce career precarity. This stress-testing will ensure that the final versions of the RCF and TTLMs are fit for purpose.

The **consultation meetings resulted in a large number of comments** across the topics of the SECURE RCF and TTLMs from the viewpoint of researchers, research organisations, and industry. It is noticeable that there has been a low level of engagement by industry in the meetings which seems to reflect the relative focus of the RCF and TTLMs on academic RPOs and RFOs, the low level of interest or priority from industry in the reform of research careers, and the potential lack of understanding on the role which industry can play in the reform of research careers. Industry should in future be encouraged to engage in shaping policies on the reform of research careers.

The **consultation survey resulted in a large number of responses** especially from researchers who were the main target group of the survey. It is noteworthy that more senior researchers (who tend to have more career stability) responded to the survey than early-career researchers (who tend to have less career stability) even though there are overall more early-career researchers. It is also noteworthy that the researchers overall prioritised all actions as TOP or HIGH with no actions coming out overall as LOW. While there are in many cases noticeable differences between the priorities, there are also in many cases relatively minimal differences between the priorities.

The comments and responses from the **consultation will guide the next stage of the project** whereby the RCF and TTLMs will be revised in discussion with the SECURE consortium. This revision is expected to include a restructuring of the RCF (which is now aligned with the pillars of the European Framework for Research Careers) into a set of action areas consisting of various actions. This revision is also expected to revise individual actions whereby actions may be kept as they are, revised, merged with other actions, or removed from the RCF. The SECURE consortium will carefully consider and weigh the feedback in their discussions to revise the RCF and TTLMs.

References

- [1] Webpage of the *Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE)* project on CORDIS hosted by the European Commission. Link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094902>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [2] O'Neill, Gareth (2024) *First Draft of SECURE Research Career Framework*. Deliverable D2.1 of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project. Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10776715>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [3] Day, Emma, Katarina Haluskova & Gareth O'Neill (2025) *Report on Consultation on SECURE Tenure Track-like Models*. Deliverable D3.2 of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project. Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/15099434>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [4] Day, Emma, Yolanda Pringle, Cornelia Van Scherpenberg, Claudia Vieira & Clare Viney (2024) *First Draft of SECURE Tenure Track-Like Models*. Deliverable D3.1 of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project. <https://zenodo.org/records/11486657>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [5] O'Neill, Gareth (2025) *SECURE Research Career Framework*. Deliverable D2.3 of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project. Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/14917414>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [6] Day, Emma (2025) *SECURE Tenure Track-Like Models*. Deliverable D3.3 of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project. Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/14917429>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [7] Moya-Falcón, Corina, Priscila Velázquez-Ortuño, Sophie Bouccara, Emma Day, Alina Irimia, Matthieu Lafon, Hélder Lopes, Nataša Jakominić Marot, Panagiotis Moiras, Gareth O'Neill, Isabel Rocha, Alexandra Roman, Ioana Trif, Ana Margarida Venda & Saša Zelenika (2025) *Report on Trials to Implement SECURE Research Career Framework*. Deliverable D4.2 of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project. Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/15099450>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [8] Council of the European Union (2023) *Council Recommendation C/2023/1640 of 18 December 2023 on a European Framework to Attract and Retain Research, Innovation, and Entrepreneurial Talents in Europe*. Link: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5250dd63-a5ec-11ee-b164-01aa75ed71a1>. Accessed 11 April 2025.

- [9] O'Neill, Gareth & Silvia Gomez Recio (2024) *Privacy Policy for SECURE Consultation Meeting for Researchers*. Link: https://secureproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/secure_wp23_consultation_meetings_researchers_privacy_v1.pdf. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [10] O'Neill, Gareth & Silvia Gomez Recio (2024) *Privacy Policy for SECURE Consultation Meeting for Research Organisations*. Link: https://secureproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/secure_wp23_consultation_meetings_organisations_privacy_v1.pdf. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [11] O'Neill, Gareth & Katarina Haluskova (2024) *Privacy Policy for SECURE Consultation Meeting for Industry Representatives*. Link: https://secureproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/secure_wp23_consultation_meetings_industry_privacy_v1.pdf. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [12] Webpage of the *European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp)* hosted by the European Commission. Link: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [13] Website of *Brainzell*. Link: <https://brainzell.com>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [14] Website of the *European Association of Research and Technology Organisations (EARTO)*. Link: <https://www.earto.eu>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [15] Council of the European Union (2023) *R1-R4 Researcher Profiles*. Published as Recommendations 5 and 6 under the Council Recommendation C/2023/1640 of 18 December 2023 on a European Framework to Attract and Retain Research, Innovation, and Entrepreneurial Talents in Europe. Link: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5250dd63-a5ec-11ee-b164-01aa75ed71a1>. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [16] Webpage of the *Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework 2024* on the website of the EU Survey Tool hosted by the European Commission. Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/SECURESURVEY2024>. The survey has been unpublished whereby the webpage is a placeholder for the survey. Accessed 11 April 2025.
- [17] O'Neill, Gareth (2024) *Privacy Policy for Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework 2024*. Link: https://secureproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/secure_wp23_consultation_survey_privacy_v1.pdf. Accessed 11 April 2025.

Annex 1 - Slides for Consultation for Researchers

SECURE Consultation for Researchers

Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group)
16 September 2024 Online

Funded by the European Union

Agenda

- 10.05: Introduction to RCF
- 10.20: Transfer to Break-outs
- 10.25: Break-out Session 1 [5 Topics]
- 10.55: Short Break
- 11.00: Break-out Session 2 [5 Topics]
- 11.30: Plenary Debrief [5 DebrieFs]
- 11.50: Question and Answers
- 12.00: Closing

02

SECURE Project

The SECURE project will develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity

03

Towards a Council Recommendation on Research Careers

14 February 2023: Technical Document for ERAC
13 July 2023: European Commission Proposal
18 December 2023: Council Recommendation

04

European Framework for Research Careers (EFFRC)

Pillar 1 Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area #1-4	Pillar 2 Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers #7-10	Pillar 3 Recruitment and Working Conditions #11-15	Pillar 4 Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation #16-25
Pillar 5 Career Assessment, Development, and Progression #26-30	Pillar 6 Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination #31-32	Pillar 7 Support Actions for Research Careers #33-39	Pillar 8 Monitoring of Research Careers #40-44

05

Links to Other Key European Initiatives

06

SECURE Research Career Framework

Interpretation of Effrc for RPOs/RFOs based on 6 questions per recommendation:

- How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs?
- Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation?
- How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?
- How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?
- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

First Draft of SECURE Research Career Framework

07

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

Recommendation 1

'Researchers' means professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new scientific knowledge based on original concepts or hypotheses. They conduct research and improve or develop concepts, theories, models, infrastructures, techniques, instrumentation, software or operational methods. Researchers may be involved fully or partially in different types of activities - such as basic or applied research, experimental development, operating research equipment in any sector of the economy or society and disseminating and valorising research results. They may also be partially involved in, among others, project management, teaching, mentoring, supporting evidence-informed policy making, open science practices, knowledge and technological transfer activities, and science communication. Researchers identify options for new research and development activities, and plan for and manage them by using high-level skills and knowledge developed through formal education and training or from experience.

08

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs?

Different organisations may adopt a different definition of 'researcher' depending on their own internal or even national regulations and policies. Differing definitions of 'researcher' can limit interoperability and comparability across organisations, sectors, and countries. The semantic meaning of 'researcher' can also differ across languages and translations. This recommendation provides a common definition which can be used across languages, organisations, sectors, and countries. Organisations could adopt this definition of 'researcher' or at least clearly communicate on their own definition of 'researcher'. Researchers could also be made explicitly aware of all of the expected activities as well as formal rights and obligations associated with their role of researcher at their organisation

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation?

- Pillar 1 > Principle 6 > The Researcher
- Pillar 4 > Principle 1 > Valuing Diverse Research Careers

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?

- The adoption and promotion of ResearchComp at an organisation could be accompanied by a clear definition of 'researcher' so that it is clear for whom ResearchComp is applicable
- Organisations could align the classification/tagging of researcher job/grant advertisements with relevant ESCO classifications for occupations, skills/competences, and qualification

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?

The definition of 'researcher' proposed in this recommendation and its adoption or refinement at an organisation could help the organisation define the scope of precarity. Any organisation aiming to reduce precarity in research careers needs to define who is at risk and who is the target of efforts to reduce precarity. Including a clear definition of 'researcher' along with the associated rights and obligations of the role of the researcher in grant/job advertisements could help researchers manage their expectations in their careers

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
- Communicate more clearly on the definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Definition of 'researcher' may already be defined in local or national regulations
- Semantic meaning of 'researcher' can differ across languages and translations
- Changing definition of 'researcher' in regulations and policies is a complex process
- Researchers may be resistant to changes regarding the definition of 'researcher'

List of Potential Implementation Actions for RPOs/RFOs

#	A	B	C
1	Pillar 4 Recommendation 1	Topic	Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
2	1	1 Researchers	Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
3	1	2 Research Managers	Communicate more clearly on definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'
4	1	2 Research Managers	Raise awareness on the wide diversity of research careers in and outside academia
5	1	2 Research Managers	Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility
6	1	2 Research Managers	Promote values of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector
7	1	2 Research Managers	Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers
8	1	2 Research Managers	Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility
9	1	2 Research Managers	Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility
10	1	2 Research Managers	Define a clear profile for research manager positions with their roles and responsibilities
11	1	2 Research Managers	Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research manager as a research career
12	1	2 Research Managers	Train researchers in research management and support transition to research manager
13	1	2 Research Managers	Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research managers
14	1	2 Research Managers	Define a clear profile for research technician positions with their roles and responsibilities
15	1	2 Research Technicians	Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research technician as a research career
16	1	2 Research Technicians	Train researchers in technical support and support transition to research technician
17	1	2 Research Technicians	Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research technicians
18	1	5 R1-R4	Adapt the R1-R4 profiles or map existing organisational profiles into the R1-R4 profiles
19	1	5 R1-R4	Refer to the R1-R4 profiles in program advertisements and relevant communication
20	1	5 R1-R4	Identify scope of precarity and propose measures to reduce precarity for R1-R4 profiles
21	1	5 R1-R4	Meet doctoral candidates in preparation with relevant working conditions and benefits
22	1	5 R1-R4	Raise awareness of and support adoption of R1-R4 profiles in the non-academic sector
23	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Adopt the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles in organisational regulations and policies
24	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Tailor support measures for career development to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups
25	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Tailor support measures to address precarity in R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups

Break-out Sessions

1
Alternative
Careers

Katarina Halušková

2
Skills
Development

Sanja Terlević

3
Working
Conditions

Silvia Gomez Recio

4
Research
Assessment

Gareth O'Neill

5
Tenure
Track

Emma Day

SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 1: Alternative Careers

Intersectoral Mobility	Alternative Careers
Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	Raise awareness on non-linear and hybrid research career paths among researchers
Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector	Integrate non-linear and hybrid research career paths into regulations and policies
Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers	Offer career development support for non-linear and hybrid research career paths
Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility	Collect and share best practices on non-linear and hybrid research career paths
Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 2: Skills Development

ResearchComp

Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences for researchers	
Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers	
Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies	
Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences	
Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp	

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 3: Working Conditions

Review and internally discuss providing commensurate remuneration for researchers	Review and internally discuss providing more permanent contracts to researchers
Review and improve support for flexible working conditions and work-life balance	Define a maximum threshold for number of fixed-term contracts and monitoring plan
Review and improve support for inclusivity, equal opportunities, and gender equality	Review and internally discuss researcher access to relevant social protection benefits
Review and improve support for academic freedom and protection against interference	Collect and share best practices on improving the working conditions for researchers
Review and improve support to researchers with the fulfillment of administrative duties	

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 4: Research Assessment

Integrate a qualitative and responsible quantitative approach into research assessment	Inform research assessors on the added value of reformed research assessment criteria
Recognise diversity of roles, activities, and outputs of researchers in research assessment	Monitor any reforms in research assessment criteria for negative and unwanted effects
Recognise research manager and research management activities in research assessment	Recognise international/intersectoral/interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility
Recognise research technician and technical support activities in research assessment	Sign the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and join CoARA as a member
Recognise research integrity and inclusivity and gender equality in research assessment	Identify structural and administrative barriers to reform research assessment systems
Recognise Open Science practices and societal impact of research in research assessment	Collect and share best practices on reforming existing research assessment systems

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 5: Tenure Track

Tenure Track-like Models	Tenure Track-like Model Principles
Review regulations and status of TTLMs in national context and locally at organisations	1 Stability
Define TTLMs in discussion and close collaboration with researchers at organisations	2 Transparency
Develop an action plan for future implementation of defined TTLMs at organisations	3 Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment
Engage with key stakeholders on TTLMs to collect and share best practices on TTLMs	4 Fair Pay and Benefits
Engage with national research-funding bodies on need for long-term funding for TTLMs	5 Recognition through Career Pathways
	6 Professional Development
	7 Inclusive and Healthy Working Environments
	8 Supportive Management
	9 Responsible Evaluation

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Annex 2 - Slides for Consultation for Research Organisations

SECURE Consultation
for Research Organisations

Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group)
17 September 2024 Online

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Agenda

- 10.05: Introduction to RCF
- 10.20: Transfer to Break-outs
- 10.25: Break-out Session 1 [5 Topics]
- 10.55: Short Break
- 11.00: Break-out Session 2 [5 Topics]
- 11.30: Plenary Debrief [5 Debriefts]
- 11.50: Question and Answers
- 12.00: Closing

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

SECURE Project

The SECURE project will develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Towards a Council Recommendation on Research Careers

14 February 2023 Technical Document for ERAC → 13 July 2023 European Commission Proposal → 18 December 2023 Council Recommendation

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

European Framework for Research Careers (EFFRC)

Pillar 1 Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area #1-4	Pillar 2 Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers #7-10	Pillar 3 Recruitment and Working Conditions #11-15	Pillar 4 Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation #16-25
Pillar 5 Career Assessment, Development, and Progression #26-30	Pillar 6 Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination #31-32	Pillar 7 Support Actions for Research Careers #33-39	Pillar 8 Monitoring of Research Careers #40-44

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Links to Other Key European Initiatives

European Charter for Researchers + European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp) + European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations Classification (ESCO)

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

SECURE Research Career Framework

Interpretation of Effrc for RPOs/RFOs based on 6 questions per recommendation:

- How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs?
- Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation?
- How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?
- How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?
- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

First Draft of SECURE Research Career Framework

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

Recommendation 1

'Researchers' means professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new scientific knowledge based on original concepts or hypotheses. They conduct research and improve or develop concepts, theories, models, infrastructures, techniques, instrumentation, software or operational methods. Researchers may be involved fully or partially in different types of activities - such as basic or applied research, experimental development, operating research equipment in any sector of the economy or society and disseminating and valorising research results. They may also be partially involved in, among others, project management, teaching, mentoring, supporting evidence-informed policy making, open science practices, knowledge and technological transfer activities, and science communication. Researchers identify options for new research and development activities, and plan for and manage them by using high-level skills and knowledge developed through formal education and training or from experience.

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Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs?

Different organisations may adopt a different definition of 'researcher' depending on their own internal or even national regulations and policies. Differing definitions of 'researcher' can limit interoperability and comparability across organisations, sectors, and countries. The semantic meaning of 'researcher' can also differ across languages and translations. This recommendation provides a common definition which can be used across languages, organisations, sectors, and countries. Organisations could adopt this definition of 'researcher' or at least clearly communicate on their own definition of 'researcher'. Researchers could also be made explicitly aware of all of the expected activities as well as formal rights and obligations associated with their role of researcher at their organisation

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation?

- Pillar 1 > Principle 6 > The Researcher
- Pillar 4 > Principle 1 > Valuing Diverse Research Careers

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?

- The adoption and promotion of ResearchComp at an organisation could be accompanied by a clear definition of 'researcher' so that it is clear for whom ResearchComp is applicable
- Organisations could align the classification/tagging of researcher job/grant advertisements with relevant ESCO classifications for occupations, skills/competences, and qualification

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?

The definition of 'researcher' proposed in this recommendation and its adoption or refinement at an organisation could help the organisation define the scope of precarity. Any organisation aiming to reduce precarity in research careers needs to define who is at risk and who is the target of efforts to reduce precarity. Including a clear definition of 'researcher' along with the associated rights and obligations of the role of the researcher in grant/job advertisements could help researchers manage their expectations in their careers

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
- Communicate more clearly on the definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Definition of 'researcher' may already be defined in local or national regulations
- Semantic meaning of 'researcher' can differ across languages and translations
- Changing definition of 'researcher' in regulations and policies is a complex process
- Researchers may be resistant to changes regarding the definition of 'researcher'

List of Potential Implementation Actions for RPOs/RFOs

#	A	B	C
1	Pillar 4 Recommendation 1	Topic	Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
2	1	1 Researchers	Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
3	1	1 Researchers	Communicate more clearly on definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'
4	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Raise awareness on the wide diversity of research careers in and outside academia
5	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectional collaboration and mobility
6	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Promote values of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector
7	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers
8	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectional collaboration and mobility
9	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Collect and share best practices on support for intersectional collaboration and mobility
10	1	3 Research Managers	Define a clear profile for research manager positions with their roles and responsibilities
11	1	3 Research Managers	Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research manager as a research career
12	1	3 Research Managers	Train researchers in research management and support transition to research manager
13	1	3 Research Managers	Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research managers
14	1	4 Research Technicians	Define a clear profile for research technician positions with their roles and responsibilities
15	1	4 Research Technicians	Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research technician as a research career
16	1	4 Research Technicians	Train researchers in technical support and support transition to research technician
17	1	4 Research Technicians	Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research technicians
18	1	5 R1-R4	Adapt the R1-R4 profiles or map existing organisational profiles into the R1-R4 profiles
19	1	5 R1-R4	Refer to the R1-R4 profiles in program advertisements and relevant communication
20	1	5 R1-R4	Identify sources of precarity and propose measures to reduce precarity for R1-R4 profiles
21	1	5 R1-R4	Meet doctoral candidates in preparation with relevant working conditions and benefits
22	1	5 R1-R4	Raise awareness of and support adoption of R1-R4 profiles in the non-academic sector
23	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Adapt the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles in organisational regulations and policies
24	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Tailor support measures for career development to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups
25	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Tailor support measures to address precarity in R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups

Break-out Sessions

1
Alternative
Careers

Katarina Halušková

2
Skills
Development

Sanja Terlević

3
Working
Conditions

Silvia Gomez Recio

4
Research
Assessment

Gareth O'Neill

5
Tenure
Track

Emma Day

SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 1: Alternative Careers

Intersectoral Mobility	Alternative Careers
Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	Raise awareness on non-linear and hybrid research career paths among researchers
Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector	Integrate non-linear and hybrid research career paths into regulations and policies
Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers	Offer career development support for non-linear and hybrid research career paths
Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility	Collect and share best practices on non-linear and hybrid research career paths
Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 2: Skills Development

ResearchComp

Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences for researchers	
Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers	
Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies	
Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences	
Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp	

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 3: Working Conditions

Review and internally discuss providing commensurate remuneration for researchers	Review and internally discuss providing more permanent contracts to researchers
Review and improve support for flexible working conditions and work-life balance	Define a maximum threshold for number of fixed-term contracts and monitoring plan
Review and improve support for inclusivity, equal opportunities, and gender equality	Review and internally discuss researcher access to relevant social protection benefits
Review and improve support for academic freedom and protection against interference	Collect and share best practices on improving the working conditions for researchers
Review and improve support to researchers with the fulfilment of administrative duties	

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 4: Research Assessment

Integrate a qualitative and responsible quantitative approach into research assessment	Inform research assessors on the added value of reformed research assessment criteria
Recognise diversity of roles, activities, and outputs of researchers in research assessment	Monitor any reforms in research assessment criteria for negative and unwanted effects
Recognise research manager and research management activities in research assessment	Recognise international/intersectoral/interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility
Recognise research technician and technical support activities in research assessment	Sign the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and join CoARA as a member
Recognise research integrity and inclusivity and gender equality in research assessment	Identify structural and administrative barriers to reform research assessment systems
Recognise Open Science practices and societal impact of research in research assessment	Collect and share best practices on reforming existing research assessment systems

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 5: Tenure Track

Tenure Track-like Models	Tenure Track-like Model Principles
Review regulations and status of TTLMs in national context and locally at organisations	1 Stability
Define TTLMs in discussion and close collaboration with researchers at organisations	2 Transparency
Develop an action plan for future implementation of defined TTLMs at organisations	3 Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment
Engage with key stakeholders on TTLMs to collect and share best practices on TTLMs	4 Fair Pay and Benefits
Engage with national research-funding bodies on need for long-term funding for TTLMs	5 Recognition through Career Pathways
	6 Professional Development
	7 Inclusive and Healthy Working Environments
	8 Supportive Management
	9 Responsible Evaluation

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Annex 3 - Slides for Consultation for Industry Representatives

SECURE Consultation for Industry

Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group)
25 September 2024 Online

SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Agenda

- 10.05: Introduction to RCF
- 10.20: Transfer to Break-outs
- 10.25: Break-out Session 1 [3 Topics]
- 10.55: Short Break
- 11.00: Break-out Session 2 [3 Topics]
- 11.30: Plenary Debrief [3 Debriefts]
- 11.50: Question and Answers
- 12.00: Closing

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

SECURE Project

The SECURE project will develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Towards a Council Recommendation on Research Careers

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

European Framework for Research Careers (EFFRC)

Pillar 1 Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area #1-4	Pillar 2 Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers #7-10	Pillar 3 Recruitment and Working Conditions #11-15	Pillar 4 Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation #16-25
Pillar 5 Career Assessment, Development, and Progression #26-30	Pillar 6 Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination #31-32	Pillar 7 Support Actions for Research Careers #33-39	Pillar 8 Monitoring of Research Careers #40-44

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Links to Other Key European Initiatives

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

SECURE Research Career Framework

Interpretation of Effrc for RPOs/RFOs based on 6 questions per recommendation:

1. How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs?
2. Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation?
3. How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?
4. How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?
5. Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
6. Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

First Draft of SECURE Research Career Framework

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SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

Recommendation 1

'Researchers' means professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new scientific knowledge based on original concepts or hypotheses. They conduct research and improve or develop concepts, theories, models, infrastructures, techniques, instrumentation, software or operational methods. Researchers may be involved fully or partially in different types of activities - such as basic or applied research, experimental development, operating research equipment in any sector of the economy or society and disseminating and valorising research results. They may also be partially involved in, among others, project management, teaching, mentoring, supporting evidence-informed policy making, open science practices, knowledge and technological transfer activities, and science communication. Researchers identify options for new research and development activities, and plan for and manage them by using high-level skills and knowledge developed through formal education and training or from experience.

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Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs?

Different organisations may adopt a different definition of 'researcher' depending on their own internal or even national regulations and policies. Differing definitions of 'researcher' can limit interoperability and comparability across organisations, sectors, and countries. The semantic meaning of 'researcher' can also differ across languages and translations. This recommendation provides a common definition which can be used across languages, organisations, sectors, and countries. Organisations could adopt this definition of 'researcher' or at least clearly communicate on their own definition of 'researcher'. Researchers could also be made explicitly aware of all of the expected activities as well as formal rights and obligations associated with their role of researcher at their organisation

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation?

- Pillar 1 > Principle 6 > The Researcher
- Pillar 4 > Principle 1 > Valuing Diverse Research Careers

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?

- The adoption and promotion of ResearchComp at an organisation could be accompanied by a clear definition of 'researcher' so that it is clear for whom ResearchComp is applicable
- Organisations could align the classification/tagging of researcher job/grant advertisements with relevant ESCO classifications for occupations, skills/competences, and qualification

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?

The definition of 'researcher' proposed in this recommendation and its adoption or refinement at an organisation could help the organisation define the scope of precarity. Any organisation aiming to reduce precarity in research careers needs to define who is at risk and who is the target of efforts to reduce precarity. Including a clear definition of 'researcher' along with the associated rights and obligations of the role of the researcher in grant/job advertisements could help researchers manage their expectations in their careers

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
- Communicate more clearly on the definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Definition of 'researcher' may already be defined in local or national regulations
- Semantic meaning of 'researcher' can differ across languages and translations
- Changing definition of 'researcher' in regulations and policies is a complex process
- Researchers may be resistant to changes regarding the definition of 'researcher'

List of Potential Implementation Actions for RPOs/RFOs

#	A	B	C
1	Pillar 4 Recommendation 1	Topic	Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
2	1	1 Researchers	Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
3	1	1 Researchers	Communicate more clearly on definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'
4	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Raise awareness on the wide diversity of research careers in and outside academia
5	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectional collaboration and mobility
6	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Promote values of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector
7	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers
8	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectional collaboration and mobility
9	1	2 Intersectional Mobility	Collect and share best practices on support for intersectional collaboration and mobility
10	1	3 Research Managers	Define a clear profile for research manager positions with their roles and responsibilities
11	1	3 Research Managers	Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research manager as a research career
12	1	3 Research Managers	Train researchers in research management and support transition to research manager
13	1	3 Research Managers	Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research managers
14	1	4 Research Technicians	Define a clear profile for research technician positions with their roles and responsibilities
15	1	4 Research Technicians	Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research technician as a research career
16	1	4 Research Technicians	Train researchers in technical support and support transition to research technician
17	1	4 Research Technicians	Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research technicians
18	1	5 R1-R4	Adapt the R1-R4 profiles or map existing organisational profiles into the R1-R4 profiles
19	1	5 R1-R4	Refer to the R1-R4 profiles in program advertisements and relevant communication
20	1	5 R1-R4	Identify scope of precarity and propose measures to reduce precarity for R1-R4 profiles
21	1	5 R1-R4	Meet doctoral candidates in preparation with relevant working conditions and benefits
22	1	5 R1-R4	Raise awareness of and support adoption of R1-R4 profiles in the non-academic sector
23	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Adopt the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles in organisational regulations and policies
24	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Tailor support measures for career development to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups
25	1	6 R1-R2/R3-R4	Tailor support measures to address precarity in R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups

Break-out Sessions

- 1 Alternative Careers
- 2 Skills Development
- 3 Working Conditions

Katarína Halušková

Sanja Terlević

Emma Day

Break-out Session 1: Alternative Careers

Intersectoral Mobility

Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility

Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector

Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers

Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility

Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility

Alternative Careers

Raise awareness on non-linear and hybrid research career paths among researchers

Integrate non-linear and hybrid research career paths into regulations and policies

Offer career development support for non-linear and hybrid research career paths

Collect and share best practices on non-linear and hybrid research career paths

Break-out Session 2: Skills Development

ResearchComp

Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences for researchers

Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers

Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies

Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences

Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp

Break-out Session 3: Working Conditions

Review and internally discuss providing commensurate remuneration for researchers

Review and improve support for flexible working conditions and work-life balance

Review and improve support for inclusivity, equal opportunities, and gender equality

Review and improve support for academic freedom and protection against interference

Review and improve support to researchers with the fulfillment of administrative duties

Review and internally discuss providing more permanent contracts to researchers

Define a maximum threshold for number of fixed-term contracts and monitoring plan

Review and internally discuss researcher access to relevant social protection benefits

Collect and share best practices on improving the working conditions for researchers

Thank you!

@secure_eu

SecureEU

info@secureproject.eu

Annex 4 - Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework

Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework 2024

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Welcome!

Welcome to this public survey on research careers and the Research Career Framework from the [SECURE project!](#)

The survey is aimed at all stages of researchers as well as research-performing and research-funding organisations.

The aim of the survey is to improve the Research Career Framework and reduce the precarity of research careers.

The Research Career Framework offers actions for organisations to improve and support the careers of researchers.

The Research Career Framework is structured around the 8 pillars of the European Framework for Research Careers:

- **Pillar 1:** Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area
- **Pillar 2:** Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers
- **Pillar 3:** Recruitment and Working Conditions
- **Pillar 4:** Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation
- **Pillar 5:** Career Assessment, Development, and Progression
- **Pillar 6:** Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination
- **Pillar 7:** Support Actions for Research Careers
- **Pillar 8:** Monitoring of Research Careers.

This survey is also structured around the pillars and asks respondents to prioritise and give their views on the actions.

Select TOP priority for critical actions, HIGH priority for important actions, and LOW priority for less relevant actions.

We will use your responses to improve the Research Career Framework and will not share your personal data publicly.

The survey consists of single choice and open response questions and will take around 20-30 minutes to complete.

1

Please respond with your own personal opinion to the questions and not from the perspective of your organisation.

See for more information on the draft Research Career Framework by SECURE: <https://zenodo.org/records/10776714>.

See for more information on the draft Tenure Track-like Models from SECURE: <https://zenodo.org/records/11486657>.

* I have read and accept the terms and conditions of the consultation survey privacy policy:

https://secureproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/secure_wp23_consultation_survey_privacy_v1.pdf

Yes

Bio

(1) What is your name?

100 character(s) maximum

* (2) What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Do not wish to disclose

* (3) What is your nationality?

- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Cyprus
- Czechia
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania

2

- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Slovak Republic
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Other

* Please specify

100 character(s) maximum

* (4) What is your country of residence?

- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Cyprus
- Czechia
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Slovak Republic
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Other

3

- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Slovak Republic
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Other

* Please specify

100 character(s) maximum

* (4) What is your country of residence?

- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Cyprus
- Czechia
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Slovak Republic
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Other

3

Please specify

100 character(s) maximum

(8) What is the name of your organisation?

100 character(s) maximum

(9) Have you heard of the following European initiatives?

	Yes	No
• European Framework for Research Careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• R1-R4 Researcher Profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• European Classification of Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations (ESCO)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• RESAVER Pension Fund	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• EURAXESS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• ERA Talent Platform	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• European Charter for Researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Research and Innovation Careers Observatory (ReICO)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Pillar 1

Pillar 1 focuses on Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area.

This includes actions on researchers, intersectoral mobility, research managers and technicians, and R1-R4 profiles.

Intersectoral mobility refers to the movement and collaboration of researchers across the different societal sectors.

The [R1-R4 profiles](#) identify 4 sequential stages in the careers of researchers from early-career to senior researchers.

The R1-R2 profiles are relevant for early-career researchers and the R3-R4 profiles are relevant for senior researchers.

(10) How would you prioritise the following actions on the definition of a 'researcher'?

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	Top	High	Low
• Adopt a common definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Communicate more clearly on definition and rights and obligations of a 'researcher'	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(11) How would you prioritise the following actions on intersectoral mobility?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the wide diversity of research careers in and outside academia	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(12) How would you prioritise the following actions on research managers?

	Top	High	Low
• Define a clear profile for research manager positions with their roles and responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research manager as a research career	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Train researchers in research management and support transition to research manager	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research managers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(13) How would you prioritise the following actions on research technicians?

	Top	High	Low
• Define a clear profile for research technician positions with their roles and responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research technician as a research career	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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• Train researchers in technical support and support transition to research technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research technicians	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(14) How would you prioritise the following actions on the R1-R4 profiles?

	Top	High	Low
• Adopt the R1-R4 profiles or map existing organisational profiles onto the R1-R4 profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Refer to the R1-R4 profiles in job/grant advertisements and relevant communications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify scope of precarity and propose measures to reduce precarity for R1-R4 profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Treat doctoral candidates as professionals with related working conditions and benefits	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Raise awareness of and support adoption of R1-R4 profiles in the non-academic sector	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(15) How would you prioritise the following actions on the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles?

	Top	High	Low
• Adopt the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles in organisational regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Tailor support measures for career development to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Tailor support measures to address precarity to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(16) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 1?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 2

Pillar 2 focuses on Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers.

This includes actions on career recognition/interoperability, career pathways, ESCO classification, and human resources.

[ESCO](#) is the multilingual classification of European skills, competences, occupations, and qualifications (for researchers).

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(17) How would you prioritise the following actions on career recognition/interoperability?

	Top	High	Low
• Track the long-term career paths of researchers at and beyond home organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on recognition and support of diverse research careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders on recognition and support of diverse research careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders on interoperability and comparability of research careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(18) How would you prioritise the following actions on career pathways?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on non-linear and hybrid research career paths among researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate non-linear and hybrid research career paths into regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Offer career development support for non-linear and hybrid research career paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on non-linear and hybrid research career paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(19) How would you prioritise the following actions on the ESCO classification?

	Top	High	Low
• Integrate (updates of) the ESCO classification into research job/grant advertisements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate (updates of) ESCO classification into local/national accreditation frameworks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify changing and emerging skills/competences, occupations, and qualifications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide recommendations for future revisions of classifications in the ESCO classification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(20) How would you prioritise the following actions on human resources?

	Top	High	Low
• Conduct a review of research career structures and career paths within organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Involve human resources officers and research staff in organisational R1-R4 mapping	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Develop clear documentation, guidelines, and communications on the R1-R4 mapping	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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• Engage with other human resources offices to share best practices on the R1-R4 profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
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(21) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 2?
1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 3

Pillar 3 focuses on Recruitment and Working Conditions.

This includes actions on recruitment/selection, working conditions, rights/obligations, and pensions /RESAVER.

RESAVER is a European pension fund which allows researchers to retain pension benefits across jobs and countries.

(22) How would you prioritise the following actions on recruitment/selection?

	Top	High	Low
• Make general recruitment and selection procedures for vacant positions publicly available	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide individual feedback to candidates on results of a specific recruitment and selection	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Inform recruiters and selectors on the value of alternative career paths and career breaks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(23) How would you prioritise the following actions on working conditions?

	Top	High	Low
• Review and internally discuss providing commensurate remuneration for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support for flexible working conditions and work-life balance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support for inclusivity, equal opportunities, and gender equality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support for academic freedom and protection against interference	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support to researchers with the fulfillment of administrative duties	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and internally discuss providing more permanent contracts to researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Define a maximum limit for the number of fixed-term contracts with a monitoring plan	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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• Review and internally discuss researcher access to relevant social protection benefits	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on improving the working conditions of researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(24) How would you prioritise the following actions on rights/obligations?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness regularly on social protection rights and obligations to all researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide individual personalised counselling on social protection rights and obligations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collaborate with external specialists in the field of social protection rights and obligations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(25) How would you prioritise the following actions on pensions/RESAVER?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness about long-term pension planning and RESAVER among researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Take part in RESAVER Pension Fund and join the consortium of member organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(26) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 3?
1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 4

Pillar 4 focuses on Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation.

This includes actions on doctoral training, ResearchComp, entrepreneurship, and interdisciplinary mobility.

ResearchComp is a framework for researchers to assess and develop relevant research and transferable skills for their careers.

Interdisciplinary mobility refers to the movement and collaboration of researchers across different /integrated research domains.

The Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training are 7 principles for organisations to improve their doctoral training programmes.

The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity is for self-regulation of research integrity across

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disciplines and sectors.

Open Science refers to the opening up of activities and results of the research life cycle (such as open access to publications).

Transferable skills are skills which can be utilised or transferred across different (research) occupations, sectors, and careers.

Entrepreneurship refers to the creation of a new company based on an original idea and assuming the related risks and rewards.

(27) How would you prioritise the following actions on doctoral training?

	Top	High	Low
• Align doctoral training programmes with Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Align doctoral training programmes with European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate policies and practices for Open Science into doctoral training programmes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(28) How would you prioritise the following actions on ResearchComp?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transferable skills/competences for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transferable skills /competences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(29) How would you prioritise the following actions on entrepreneurship?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on entrepreneurship taking an inclusive and gender equal approach	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Encourage, train, and support researchers for entrepreneurship, start-ups, and spin-offs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Create support offices, hubs, and centres for entrepreneurship and technology transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11

(30) How would you prioritise the following actions on interdisciplinary mobility?

	Top	High	Low
• Encourage, train, and support researchers for interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on supporting interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(31) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 4?
1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 5

Pillar 5 focuses on Career Assessment, Development, and Progression.

This includes actions on mobility recognition, research assessment, career support, and tenure track-like models.

In a tenure track-like model (TTLM) a fixed-term contract leads to a permanent position subject to positive evaluation.

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) consists of organisations aiming to reform research assessment.

(32) How would you prioritise the following actions on mobility recognition?

	Top	High	Low
• Recognise international collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise intersectoral collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise virtual collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(33) How would you prioritise the following actions on research assessment?

	Top	High	Low
• Integrate a qualitative and responsible quantitative approach into research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise diversity of roles, activities, and outputs of researchers in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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• Recognise research manager and research management activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise research technician and technical support activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise research integrity and inclusivity and gender equality in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise Open Science practices and societal impact of research in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Inform research assessors on the added value of reformed research assessment criteria	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Monitor any reforms in research assessment criteria for negative and unwanted effects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(34) How would you prioritise the following actions on assessment initiatives?

	Top	High	Low
• Sign the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and join CoARA as a member	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify structural and administrative barriers to reform research assessment systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on reforming existing research assessment systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(35) How would you prioritise the following actions on career support?

	Top	High	Low
• Review and improve the career support and professional development of researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide professional mentoring to researchers by experts in and outside organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(36) How would you prioritise the following actions on TTLMs?

	Top	High	Low
• Review regulations and status of TTLMs in national context and locally at organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Define TTLMs in discussion and close collaboration with researchers at organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Develop an action plan for future implementation of defined TTLMs at organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders on TTLMs to collect and share best practices on TTLMs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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• Engage with national research funders on the need for long-term funding for TTLMs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
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(37) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 5?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 6

Pillar 6 focuses on Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination.

This includes actions on making the European Union attractive to researchers.

The balanced circulation of researchers refers to the movement of researchers equally to and from countries in Europe.

(38) How would you prioritise the following actions on a competitive European Union?

	Top	High	Low
• Review and internally discuss support to attract and reintegrate returning researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and internally discuss support to facilitate dual positions in different countries	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders to contribute to the balanced circulation of researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(39) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 6?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 7

Pillar 7 focuses on Support Actions for Research Careers.

This includes actions on talent platforms, European Charter for Researchers, and Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R).

EURAXESS is a European network and platform to foster the mobility and career development of researchers.

The ERA Talent Platform is an online gateway offering a range of services to support researchers and organisations.

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The [European Charter for Researchers](#) is a set of principles defining the relationship between researchers and employers/funders.

The [HRS4R](#) is a defined process to implement the European Charter for Researchers at organisations and is linked to an award.

(40) How would you prioritise the following actions on talent platforms?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the EURAXESS portal and ERA Talent Platform among researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Disseminate job/grant opportunities in the EURAXESS portal and ERA Talent Platform	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(41) How would you prioritise the following actions on the European Charter for Researchers?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the European Charter for Researchers among researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Endorse and implement the European Charter for Researchers at organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(42) How would you prioritise the following actions on the HRS4R award?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the HRS4R award and its relevance for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Apply formally to the European Commission to receive the HRS4R award	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(43) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 7?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 8

Pillar 8 focuses on the Monitoring of Research Careers.

This includes actions on the new Research and Innovation Careers Observatory (ReICO).

ReICO is a new tool being developed which aims to be the main source for reliable data and information on research careers.

ReICO is a joint initiative by the European Commission and Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD).

(44) How would you prioritise the following actions on ReICO?

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	Top	High	Low
• Engage with OECD and key stakeholders on development and implementation of ReICO	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and internally discuss collection and provision of relevant internal data for ReICO	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(45) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 8?

1000 character(s) maximum

TTLMs

The SECURE project has developed 9 principles to define tenure track-like models (TTLMs):

(1) **Stability:** Researchers expect to have a clear and defined progression pathway that leads to permanent employment or an open-ended contract.

(2) **Transparency:** Researchers expect to have been thoroughly informed about the recruitment process, expected skills and competencies, selection criteria, working conditions and benefits, contractual status, and progression pathway(s).

(3) **Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment:** Researchers expect a competitive recruitment process with selection criteria that consider a diverse range of skills, competencies, and experiences (including intersectoral) in an inclusive and accessible manner.

(4) **Fair Pay and Benefits:** Researchers expect to receive attractive and commensurate remuneration and benefits with pay increases linked to progression, and to be made aware of the review of remuneration conditions, for example once they are successful in obtaining a permanent or open-ended contract. This should include access to adequate social protection.

(5) **Recognition through Career Pathways:** Researchers expect to be supported to pursue their career ambitions, with recognition for diverse contributions and outputs (e.g. across research, teaching, leadership, innovation, and engagement) through a range of possible career pathways. Where possible this should include the opportunity for non-linear, multi-career, and hybrid paths that are recognised on par with linear career paths.

(6) **Professional Development:** Researchers expect to have the time and ability to engage in meaningful professional and career development, including access to relevant training and opportunities (including in other sectors) that develop the leadership qualities necessary for academic progression and independence. Mentoring schemes should also be offered.

(7) **Inclusive and Healthy Working Environments:** Researchers expect to work in environments that welcome and value diversity, which are healthy and accessible, and have no tolerance for bullying, harassment, or pressure to compromise research integrity.

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(8) **Supportive Management:** Researchers expect to have a named line manager (or named senior member of staff) with allocated time, availability, and expertise to offer them regular points to check in, appraise their performance, and provide the support needed to achieve their full potential.

(9) **Responsible Evaluation:** Researchers expect there to be a formal evaluation process at set checkpoints and against clear criteria. These criteria and timeline should be made available to them before or at the time of appointment. Where it becomes clear that they may not meet the criteria, researchers expect this to be communicated as early as possible and a support plan and process of remediation should be put in place.

(46) How would you prioritise the following principles for TTLMs?

	Top	High	Low
• Stability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Transparency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Fair Pay and Benefits	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognition through Career Pathways	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Professional Development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Inclusive and Healthy Working Environments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Supportive Management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Responsible Evaluation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(47) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above principles for TTLMs?

1000 character(s) maximum

(48) What do you think are the main reasons for the precarity of research careers?

1000 character(s) maximum

• (49) Do you think TTLMs are the ideal way to reduce the precarity of research careers?

- Yes
 No

• Please explain

1000 character(s) maximum

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(50) Do you have any final comments on the actions of the Research Career Framework or principles for TTLMs?

1000 character(s) maximum

Thank You!

Thank you for taking the time to respond to this survey and help the SECURE project to improve research careers in Europe!

• Would you like to be kept informed of the results of the survey and the SECURE project?

- Yes
 No

• Please enter your email address

100 character(s) maximum

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***Report on Consultation on
SECURE Research Career Framework***

***Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group)
& Katarina Haluskova (ABIS)***

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secureproject.eu